

Valorisation of an indigenous breed: Quality keys

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Calves and fattened calves of the Pajuna breed in Sierra Nevada, Cortijo de Cortes, Granada. Animals raised by Torcuato Aguilera Cabrerizo.

The Pajuna breed of cattle is an indigenous breed of Spain, recognised for its resistance and adaptation to the mountain environment. It is originally from Andalusia and it has been historically bred in mountainous areas such as the Sierra Nevada, where its hardiness makes it a key element in sustainable livestock farming and in the preservation of unique ecosystems.

The Pajuna breed belongs to the Iberian bovine stock and it is a medium-sized, agile and light breed. As a native breed, it retains a valuable genetic heritage, including disease resistance and adaptation to extreme climates. Although their productivity is lower than specialised breeds, their organoleptic quality compensates for this lower production.

The system under study is based on the production of pure-bred Pajuna cattle, classified into three batches. The first batch, comprising 15% of the production, is fattened on pasture on a farm owned by the Sierra Nevada National Park (Cortijo de Cortes), consisting of castrated males, which are fed on pasture from weaning to 24 months, and are slaughtered at 300 kg live weight with a carcass yield of 53%. They are marketed either through direct sales to the final consumer or in local butchers' shops.

The second batch, a small group of animals, 10% of the total, are reared for 30 months on pasture, but in a different location, and the producer himself is responsible for the processing and direct marketing of the final product.

The remaining 75 % are sent to a local feedlot, where they reach slaughter weight at 17 months and are marketed in a local butcher's shop linked to the feedlot itself.

This diversification of production helps to reduce economic risk, and it has also made it possible to deepen the characteristics that the production system confers on the final product, so that animals that have been reared for 24-30 months in the field and whose diet is based mainly on the consumption of mountain pasture, are able to withstand maturation periods of up to 20 days after slaughter. During this period, losses can be up to 10%, but this reduction in total yield is compensated by an increase in the tenderness and palatability of the final product.

On the other hand, animals fattened only on feed, although they share with grass-fed animals a high content of healthy fatty acids, the unique red colour and flavour, do not withstand such a long maturation period in the butchering process, which affects the tenderness and intensity of the flavour.

Therefore, these three elements - breed, mountain pasture and meat maturation - are the keys to obtaining high quality meat, which is in great demand at local level.

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